

Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean

Short and Long-term Climate Projections are Ready for All Demo Sites

VERSION 1.0

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	10
2. Demo sites and meteorological data	11
2.1. Imputation of missing values	13
2.1.1. MICE package	14
2.1.2. Selected imputation methods for each demo site	14
3. Climate datasets.....	24
3.1. Long-term climate projections	25
3.1.1. Mediterranean scale.....	26
3.1.2. Demo site scale.....	32
3.2. Short term climate predictions	32
3.2.1. Demo site scale.....	33
3.3. Near term climate forecasts	34
4. Appendix.....	37
4.1. MICE imputation methods.....	37
4.2. Convolutional neural network	38
4.3. Quantile delta mapping.....	39
5. References.....	41

List of Tables

Table 1. Main characteristics of the demo sites. 12

Table 2. List of the selected GCMs..... 26

Table 3. RMSE evaluated in the test phase between ERA5 0.25° data and CNN outputs at daily and monthly scales over the MED region..... 29

Table 4. List of the selected GCMs..... 32

Table 5. Summary of weather forecasting models selected for application in the Bode demo site, including their key characteristics..... 36

List of Figures

Figure 1. Location of the demo sites (squares with abbreviations listed in Table 1). MedECC-MAR1 region (dashed line) and domain coordinates. 11

Figure 2. Total number of rainfall stations provided by partners and the number of rainfall stations retained for climate model bias correction. The number at the top of each column represents the count of provided/useful stations..... 12

Figure 3. Total number of temperature stations provided by partners and the number of temperature stations retained for climate model bias correction. The number at the top of each column represents the count of provided/useful stations. Stations with mean temperature records are shown on the left, while those with maximum and minimum temperature records are shown on the right. 13

Figure 4. Procedural scheme for imputing missing data in precipitation and temperature time series..... 13

Figure 5. Rainfall time series for one of the Bode gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data. 15

Figure 6. Mean temperature time series for one of the Bode gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data..... 15

Figure 7. Rainfall time series for one of the Albufera gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while

the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data. 16

Figure 8. Mean temperature time series for one of the Albufera gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data. 17

Figure 9. Rainfall time series for one of the Agia gauging stations after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red. 18

Figure 10. Mean temperature time series for one of the Agia gauging stations after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red. 18

Figure 11. Maximum temperature time series for the gauging station in Arborea after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red. 19

Figure 12. Rainfall time series for one of the Mujib gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data. 19

Figure 13. Mean temperature time series for one of the Mujib gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data. 20

Figure 14. Rainfall time series for one of the Sebou gauging stations after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red. 21

Figure 15. Rainfall time series for one of the Medjerda gauging stations after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red. 22

Figure 16. Mean temperature time series for one of the Medjerda gauging stations after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red. 22

Figure 17. Rainfall time series for one of the Konya gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data. 23

Figure 18. Mean temperature time series for one of the Konya gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in

red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data..... 23

Figure 19. Procedural diagram for generating climate datasets. Acronyms: GCM – General Circulation Model, CNN – Convolutional Neural Network, QM – Quantile Mapping, QDM – Quantile Delta Mapping, NN – Nearest Neighbour. 25

Figure 20. Location of the demo sites (squares with abbreviations listed in Table 1). MedECC-MAR1 region (red dashed line) and extended Mediterranean area (black dashed line), together with their domain coordinates. 27

Figure 21. CNN architecture used to enhance GCM spatial resolution in the MED region. 29

Figure 22. Daily precipitation (October 12, 2049) for model GFDL-ESM4 and scenario SSP126..... 29

Figure 23. Daily mean temperature (October 12, 2049) for model GFDL-ESM4 and scenario SSP126..... 30

Figure 24. ECDF of observed precipitation (blue points), raw climate model output (green points), and QDM-corrected precipitation (orange points) over the historical reference period (1985–2014) at location (lon -4.5°, lat 33.5°) for model GFDL-ESM4. 31

Figure 25. ECDF of observed mean temperature (blue points), raw climate model output (green points), and QDM-corrected mean temperature (orange points) over the historical reference period (1985–2014) at location (lon -4.5°, lat 33.5°) for model GFDL-ESM4. 31

Figure 26. CNN architecture used to enhance DCPG GCM spatial resolution at the Bode demo site. 34

Acronyms

AGRI	AgroInsider
BU	Boğaziçi University
CW	Constructed Wetlands
ESIM	Higher School of Engineering of Medjez El Bab
IDRICA	Idrica
LPM	Living Planet Morocco
MED	Mediterranean
MRB	Mujib River Basin
NbS	Nature-based solution
NVZ	Nitrates Vulnerable Zone
PMM	Predictive Mean Matching
RF	Random Forest
RSCN	Royal Society for the Conservation of Nature
RSS	Remote Sensing Solutions GmbH
SEMIDE	Euro-Mediterranean Information System on know-how in the Water sector
TdV	La Tour du Valat
TUC	Technical University of Crete
UFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research
UNINA	University of Naples Federico II
UNIPR	University of Parma
UNISS	University of Sassari
UPV	Universitat Politècnica de València

Executive summary

The overall objective of the "Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean" (OurMED) project is to design and explore innovative and sustainable storage and distribution systems tightly integrated into ecosystem management at the river basin scale. This is achieved by the combination of scientific and local knowledge, emerging from new and long-lasting spaces for social learning among interdependent stakeholders, society actors and scientific researchers in eight local and one regional MED demo sites. OurMED calls for a transition from a mono-sectoral water management approach based on trade-offs, to equitable multi-sectoral and integrative management that addresses all water bodies' capabilities and needs towards sustainability.

Milestone 4.3 (M4.3), is part of Task 4.3 "Collection of future climate projections at the demo site locations" (Lead: UNIPR/ Participants: UFZ, RSS, UPV, IDRICA, TdV, TUC, UNISS, UNINA, RSCN, LPM, AGRI, ESIM, BU), (M6-M24). Milestone 4.3, "Short and long-term climate projections are ready for all demo sites", presents a comprehensive report outlining the data and methodologies used to obtain climate datasets over both short-term and long-term horizons. These datasets, which include precipitation and temperature data—two key components of the hydrological cycle—will support water management and decision-making at the demo sites by providing essential information for mitigating the effects of climate change.

1. Introduction

The “Sustainable Water Storage and Distribution in The Mediterranean” (OurMED) is an EU-funded project operating under Grant Agreement Number 2222. OurMED aims to design and explore innovative, sustainable storage and distribution systems integrated into ecosystem management at the river basin scale.

To achieve these objectives, OurMED recognizes that addressing the impacts of climate change requires advanced knowledge and intervention capabilities across both short- and long-term horizons. In this context, Milestone 4.3 represents a critical step in the project efforts to address climate change challenges. This milestone focuses on establishing the data and methodologies required to obtain reliable climate datasets for the demo sites, including, in some cases, the regional MED demo site. The climate datasets consist of long-term projections (until 2100), short-term predictions (1 to 10 years), and near-term forecasts (next days to months).

For each demo site, historical records of precipitation and temperature at the station scale were collected as part of WP2 (Varouchakis et al., 2024), and any gaps in the data were filled using specialized techniques to ensure a continuous and reliable dataset. Within OurMED this step is essential for generating accurate local-scale long-term projections and short-term predictions by correcting the systematic errors (biases) they often exhibit.

Long-term climate projections and short-term predictions are derived from data provided by climate models participating in the latest Coupled Model Intercomparison Project 6 (CMIP6 - Eyring et al., 2016). Specifically, long-term projections rely on data from the Scenario Model Intercomparison Project (ScenarioMIP - O'Neill et al., 2016; Tebaldi et al., 2021) and, within OurMED, are downscaled at both the MED scale and the demo site scale. These projections extend until the end of the century and consider different Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs - O'Neill et al., 2017). Short-term predictions, covering a time horizon of 1 to 10 years, are analysed exclusively at the demo site scale using data from the Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP - Boer et al., 2016). Near-term forecasts, spanning the next few days to months, are provided by national and international institutes and are considered only for demo sites where models simulate outcomes at this temporal scale.

The climate datasets will support ongoing research and applications within Task 4.2, WP3, WP5 and WP7, enhancing the overall resilience of the demo sites involved.

2. Demo sites and meteorological data

In OurMED, long-term climate projections and short-term climate predictions are downscaled at the scale of the eight demo sites. The demo sites are located in Germany (Bode), Spain (Albufera), Greece (Agia), Italy (Arborea), Jordan (Mujib), Morocco (Sebou), Tunisia (Medjerda), and Turkey (Konya), as shown in **Figure 1**. Table 1 summarizes the key characteristics of the demo sites.

As previously mentioned, long-term projections also consider the regional MED demo site. These projections are downscaled over the MedECC-MAR1 (MedECC, 2020) domain (longitude: 10°W–39°E; latitude: 29°N–47.5°N), which encompasses all demo sites except Bode.

Figure 1. Location of the demo sites (squares with abbreviations listed in Table 1). MedECC-MAR1 region (dashed line) and domain coordinates.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the demo sites.

Nation	Demo site name	Abbreviation	Size (km ²)
Germany	Bode	GER	3300
Spain	Albufera	SPA	116
Greece	Agia	GRE	210
Italy	Arborea	ITA	1193
Jordan	Mujib	JOR	6600
Morocco	Sebou	MOR	39500
Tunisia	Medjerda	TUN	23659
Turkey	Konya	TUR	50000

For each demo site, historical records of daily precipitation and mean, minimum and maximum temperature from available gauging stations were collected (Varouchakis et al., 2024). Only stations with time series containing more than 65% of the data for the period 1985–2014 (chosen as the control period for climate model bias correction) were selected for further analysis. **Figure 2** and **Figure 3** show the number of meteorological stations retained, compared to the total number of stations provided by the partners.

Figure 2. Total number of rainfall stations provided by partners and the number of rainfall stations retained for climate model bias correction. The number at the top of each column represents the count of provided/useful stations.

Figure 3. Total number of temperature stations provided by partners and the number of temperature stations retained for climate model bias correction. The number at the top of each column represents the count of provided/useful stations. Stations with mean temperature records are shown on the left, while those with maximum and minimum temperature records are shown on the right.

2.1. Imputation of missing values

The historical records collected for the demo sites contain periods with varying lengths of missing data. For the stations with more than 65% of data for the period 1985–2014 (Figure 2 and Figure 3), gaps in the data were filled using the procedural framework outlined in Figure 4. For each demo site, the imputation process primarily relies on data from correlated stations with available records. Additionally, observational and reanalysis datasets, such as E-OBS (Cornes et al., 2018) and ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2020), were used to support imputation in cases where meteorological stations or records were limited. The Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE) package (van Buuren & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011) was used in the imputation process. This process allows obtaining sufficiently long (30 years) continuous historical time series, which are essential for generating accurate local-scale climate model data by correcting, during the downscaling process, the systematic errors (biases) they often exhibit.

Figure 4. Procedural scheme for imputing missing data in precipitation and temperature time series.

2.1.1. MICE package

The MICE package in the R programming environment was used to handle missing data through multiple imputation, addressing at the same time the uncertainty inherent in the imputation process. The proposed methodology for reconstructing time series with missing data consists of a two-step approach designed to enhance the reliability and accuracy of the dataset.

The first step involves a preliminary assessment of the missing data patterns, facilitating the selection of an appropriate imputation method. Once the nature of the missing data is established, multiple imputations are performed to estimate the missing values. These values are estimated iteratively using chained equations, where each variable with missing data is modeled conditionally based on other variables in the dataset. The choice of the imputation method, such as predictive mean matching (PMM), random forest (RF), or another algorithm, is based on the characteristics of the data and the relationships among the variables. The imputation process generates several datasets (realizations), typically five or more, each with different plausible values for the missing entries.

In the second step, these multiple realizations are further refined to reconstruct the time series for each station with gaps in its original data. Specifically, a multiple linear regression model is fitted for each station with missing data, utilizing the now-complete data from other stations as predictors. To ensure robust predictions, stations with stronger correlations to the target station are assigned higher weights within the regression model. Additionally, a threshold based on the Pearson correlation coefficient is applied to exclude weakly correlated stations, reducing noise and preventing irrelevant predictors from influencing the results. Given the availability of multiple imputed datasets, a separate regression model is constructed for each realization, acknowledging the variability introduced during imputation. The final reconstructed time series for each target station is obtained by averaging the predictions from all regression models across the realizations.

Finally, the entire process is guided by a rigorous physical consistency framework, ensuring that the reconstructed data align with fundamental climatic principles. In particular, the methodology enforces that maximum temperatures are always greater than mean temperatures, which in turn are higher than minimum temperatures. Additionally, for precipitation, the methodology ensures that the reconstructed time series does not contain values below zero, as negative precipitation is physically meaningless.

More details about the imputation methods are reported in Section 4.1 (Appendix).

2.1.2. Selected imputation methods for each demo site

This section provides a concise description of the process used to obtain complete time series for each demo site. To illustrate the results, this study adopts the Abayomi convention for color representation (Abayomi et al., 2008): blue represents the observed portion of the data, red denotes the estimated values.

Bode (Germany)

The method employed is the RF for both precipitation and temperature data, generating 20 different imputed datasets (realizations). A minimum Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.7 was set to determine which stations to include in the imputation process. For illustration purposes, **Figure 5** and **Figure 6** present two imputed time series for precipitation and mean temperature, respectively, along with the uncertainty in the imputation process, represented by the standard deviation.

Figure 5. Rainfall time series for one of the Bode gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data.

Figure 6. Mean temperature time series for one of the Bode gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data.

Albufera (Spain)

The method employed is the RF for both precipitation and temperature data, generating 20 different imputed datasets (realizations). A minimum Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.7 was set to determine which stations to include in the imputation process. Since only two meteorological stations were available for this demo site, with one having significant gaps, data from E-OBS were incorporated to simulate additional meteorological stations during the imputation process. For illustration purposes, **Figure 7** and **Figure 8** present two imputed time series for precipitation and mean temperature, respectively, along with the uncertainty in the imputation process, represented by the standard deviation. It can be noted that the filling percentage is above 35%; however, since only two meteorological stations were available, both were retained, contrary to the criterion stated in Section 2.2, which specifies that only stations with more than 65% data coverage during the control period (1985–2014) would be retained.

Figure 7. Rainfall time series for one of the Albufera gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data.

Figure 8. Mean temperature time series for one of the Albufera gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data.

Agia (Greece)

The method employed for imputing precipitation data is the PMM, which generates 20 distinct imputed datasets (realizations). Due to limited data availability, developing a non-linear imputation model, such as RF, was impractical. Unlike RF, PMM relies on patterns within the available data rather than complex relationships. Additionally, E-OBS data were used to fill gaps in the records of the three retained rainfall stations. Companion stations were selected based on a minimum Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.5. The imputation process was conducted on a monthly basis, meaning data for each month (e.g., all January data, all February data, etc.) were analyzed independently.

The method employed for imputing temperature data is the RF, which generates 20 distinct imputed datasets (realizations). A minimum Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.7 was applied to determine the stations included in the imputation process. Due to the availability of only two temperature stations for this demo site, ERA5 data were incorporated to simulate additional meteorological stations during the imputation process. ERA5 was preferred over E-OBS for temperature data, as E-OBS exhibits physical inconsistencies in specific locations like Crete, where the minimum temperature can be higher than the mean or maximum temperature, rendering it less reliable for this purpose.

Due to the nature of this process, it was not possible to estimate uncertainty for the imputed time series. For illustration purposes, **Figure 9** and **Figure 10** present two imputed time series for precipitation and mean temperature, respectively.

Figure 9. Rainfall time series for one of the Agia gauging stations after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red.

Figure 10. Mean temperature time series for one of the Agia gauging stations after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red.

Arborea (Italy)

For the Italian demo site, only one meteorological station was available. Precipitation data were complete, while temperature data had scattered gaps, with only maximum and minimum temperature values recorded. To address the gaps in the temperature series, a random sampling approach was used for imputation. **Figure 11** illustrates the imputed time series for maximum temperature. Since only a single realization was considered, it was not possible to assign uncertainty to the imputed time series.

Figure 11. Maximum temperature time series for the gauging station in Arborea after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red.

Mujib (Jordan)

The method employed is the RF for both precipitation and temperature data, generating 20 different imputed datasets (realizations). A minimum Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.7 was set to determine which stations to include in the imputation process. For illustration purposes, **Figure 12** and **Figure 13** present two imputed time series for precipitation and mean temperature, respectively, along with the uncertainty in the imputation process, represented by the standard deviation.

Figure 12. Rainfall time series for one of the Mujib gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data.

Figure 13. Mean temperature time series for one of the Mujib gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data.

Sebou (Morocco)

In Morocco, many gauging stations are recent and lack sufficient records to cover the selected control period. After analysing the available data, only two precipitation stations were retained, which presented contemporaneous data gaps. To address this, ERA5 data (selected for the same reason previously explained for the Agia demo site) were used to fill the missing data. A simple linear regression model was applied, utilizing the station/grid node with the highest correlation to the station with missing data. Following this procedure, the remaining gaps were filled using the RF method from the MICE package, generating 20 imputed datasets (realizations) and considering a minimum Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.5 to select companion stations. No temperature stations were retained, and gridded datasets were then used as a reference to construct the historical meteorological dataset. Due to the nature of this process, it was not possible to estimate uncertainty for the imputed time series. **Figure 14** presents an example of an imputed time series for a precipitation station.

Figure 14. Rainfall time series for one of the Sebou gauging stations after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red.

Medjerda (Tunisia)

In Tunisia, data from numerous precipitation gauging stations were available. After a thorough screening of the collected data, 61 stations were retained for further use. Following a similar approach to that employed for Morocco, rainfall time series were initially filled using linear regression between the station with gaps and the most correlated station with available data. A minimum Pearson correlation threshold of 0.6 was applied to identify companion stations. Once this procedure was completed, any remaining gaps were imputed by analysing the data on a monthly basis and randomly sampling values to fill the missing data. Due to the nature of this process, it was not possible to estimate uncertainty for the imputed time series. For temperature, only four stations were retained, providing maximum and minimum temperature data. The missing values were imputed using the Random Forest (RF) method, generating 20 imputed datasets (realizations) and applying a minimum Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.7 to select stations included in the imputation process. For illustration purposes, **Figure 15** and **Figure 16** present two imputed time series for precipitation and maximum temperature, respectively.

Figure 15. Rainfall time series for one of the Medjerda gauging stations after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red.

Figure 16. Mean temperature time series for one of the Medjerda gauging stations after imputation. The figure depicts the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red.

Konya (Turkey)

The method employed is the RF for both precipitation and temperature data, generating 20 different imputed datasets (realizations). A minimum Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.7 was set to determine which stations to include in the imputation process. For illustration purposes, **Figure 17** and **Figure 18** present two imputed time series for precipitation and mean temperature, respectively, along with the uncertainty in the imputation process, represented by the standard deviation.

Figure 17. Rainfall time series for one of the Konya gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data.

Figure 18. Mean temperature time series for one of the Konya gauging stations after imputation. The top panel presents the observed data in blue and the imputed values in red, while the bottom panel depicts the standard deviation to represent the uncertainty in the imputed data.

3. Climate datasets

Climate simulations are essential for evaluating the impacts of climate variability and change, as well as for developing effective adaptation and mitigation strategies. Climate simulations vary with the temporal scale, transitioning from an initial value problem at shorter timescales (days to months) to a forced boundary-value problem at longer timescales (decades to century). Near-term forecasts rely on current atmospheric conditions, while long-term projections are primarily driven by external forcing. Short-term predictions (years to decades) represent a transition, influenced by both initial conditions and external forcing factors (Boer et al., 2016).

In particular, long-term projections, extending up to 2100, provide insights into potential changes in climate variables such as temperature and precipitation under different scenarios. The latest scenario framework, the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) (O'Neill et al., 2017), explores the consequences of different greenhouse gas emission trajectories and socioeconomic developments. These projections are primarily used for strategic planning, policymaking, and assessing long-term sustainability and resilience. For instance, they support the evaluation of large-scale water storage and distribution systems, incorporating uncertainties inherent in long-term climate scenarios (IPCC, 2021). Applications include infrastructure design, land-use planning, and the development of nature-based solutions.

Short-term (decadal) predictions, typically covering 1 to 10 years, are based on initialized simulations that incorporate the observed state of the climate system. Unlike long-term projections, they are less influenced by greenhouse gas scenarios and more dependent on natural climate variability. These predictions are particularly useful for short-term resource planning and risk management, enabling the development of adaptive management strategies at regional or local scales. This is especially relevant for climate-sensitive sectors such as water and agriculture, where stakeholders can anticipate and mitigate risks based on expected climatic trends. The Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP) highlights the potential of these simulations to provide predictions for phenomena such as droughts and wet periods, directly impacting water availability and demand (Boer et al., 2016).

Finally, near-term forecasts, covering timescales from days to months, are highly operational and dynamic. These forecasts use real-time climate data and high-resolution models to provide actionable information for immediate decision-making. They are used in early warning systems, enhancing preparedness and resilience against extreme events. Near-term forecasts also support seasonal planning, such as optimizing irrigation schedules or managing reservoir levels in response to changing precipitation patterns. Their accuracy and usefulness depend on the availability of localized models and observational data that capture fine-scale dynamics relevant to specific regions or catchments. These simulations are typically produced by national and international institutes.

Figure 19 schematically illustrates the methodologies used in OurMED for generating climate projections across these time horizons, as detailed in the following sections.

Figure 19. Procedural diagram for generating climate datasets. Acronyms: GCM – General Circulation Model, CNN – Convolutional Neural Network, QM – Quantile Mapping, QDM – Quantile Delta Mapping, NN – Nearest Neighbour.

3.1. Long-term climate projections

For long-term projections of precipitation and temperature, climate models from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) were selected (Eyring et al., 2016). CMIP6 was prioritized because it incorporates the latest advancements in the representation of physical processes within climate models and aligns with the most recent climate scenarios, the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs - O’Neill et al., 2017), as outlined in the latest IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6 – IPCC, 2021). Currently, only climate projections from General Circulation Models (GCMs) are available, as dynamical downscaling to enhance GCM resolution is still underway within the COordinated Regional Downscaling EXperiment (CORDEX) initiative (Gutowski Jr. et al., 2016). As a result, CMIP6 Regional Climate Model (RCM) projections are not yet available for the OurMED domain.

To address the coarse spatial resolution of CMIP6-GCMs (approximately 1° or more), within the OurMED project, advanced statistical downscaling techniques were developed. These methods effectively refine global model outputs into higher-resolution projections, making them suitable for regional and local-scale analysis. Statistical downscaling is now widely recognized by the scientific community as a reliable and computationally efficient approach. Its importance is further highlighted by its inclusion in the official documentation of the second phase of the CORDEX experiment, titled “CORDEX experiment design and archiving specifications for statistical downscaling of CMIP6” (CORDEX, 2024).

To account for the uncertainty in climate model projections, an ensemble of GCMs and two SSP scenarios are examined within OurMED. Each SSP reflects projections of demographic and economic growth, as well as trends in technological and geopolitical developments (O’Neill et al., 2017)—all of which influence emissions and the potential for mitigation or adaptation. Additionally, each SSP is paired with different emission pathways, the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), offering a more detailed and comprehensive view of future climate scenarios.

In the OURMED project, five specific GCMs (**Table 2**) were chosen based on recommendations provided by two official CORDEX documents: “EURO-CORDEX CMIP6

GCM Selection & Ensemble Design: Best Practices and Recommendations” (for dynamic downscaling - Sobolowski et al., 2023) and “CORDEX experiment design and archiving specifications for statistical downscaling of CMIP6” (for statistical downscaling - CORDEX, 2024). These documents identify particular GCMs and experiments as the most reliable options for downscaling. From this pool of recommended models, the final selection of five GCMs was made based on the following criteria: (i) the models selected offer relatively high spatial resolution at the native global scale and (ii) key variables (precipitation, mean temperature, maximum temperature, and minimum temperature) are available within the model datasets. Regarding the choice of scenarios, the same CORDEX documents prioritize two: SSP1-2.6 and SSP3-7.0, for future climate analyses. SSP1-2.6 represents a low-emission, sustainable development pathway, while SSP3-7.0 reflects a higher-emission scenario driven by regional rivalry. Following these guidelines ensures consistency with the broader scientific community and enables comparability with other studies.

Table 2. List of the selected GCMs.

	GCM institute	Model	Grid resolution (Lon x Lat)
1	NCC	NorESM2-MM	1.25° x 0.94°
2	DKRZ	MPI-ESM1-2-HR	0.94° x 0.94°
3	EC-Earth-Consortium	EC-Earth3-Veg	0.70° x 0.70°
4	NOAA-GFDL	GFDL-ESM4	1.25° x 1.00°
5	MRI	MRI-ESM2-0	1.13° x 1.12°

As part of the OURMED project, the selected GCMs were initially downscaled to the MED scale, providing a solid foundation for identifying large-scale climate trends and patterns. This step is essential for developing regional and national adaptation strategies and supports transboundary climate risk assessments. Building on this, the projections are further downscaled to the level of the demo sites. These projections enable the creation of tailored adaptation strategies, improving resource management, and offering a more detailed understanding of climate impacts at the site-specific level.

The following paragraphs describe the downscaling methods developed to obtain high-resolution climate projections at the different scales considered.

3.1.1. Mediterranean scale

For the regional MED demo site, the domain defined in the First Mediterranean Assessment Report (MEDECC-MAR1) is used to present climate results (as already shown in **Figure 1**). However, to facilitate analysis at the state-level across the entire Mediterranean area, an extended domain (longitude: 18.5°W–45.25°E; latitude: 18.5°N–53.25°N) has been adopted within the OurMED Consortium (**Figure 20**). Therefore,

statistical downscaling of GCM data was performed on this domain, which, in addition to the MED states, encompasses all eight demo sites. Climate projections for these domains result at a resolution of 0.25°.

Figure 20. Location of the demo sites (squares with abbreviations listed in Table 1). MedECC-MAR1 region (red dashed line) and extended Mediterranean area (black dashed line), together with their domain coordinates.

3.1.1.1. Statistical downscaling of long-term climate projections

Statistical downscaling is a technique used to translate coarse-resolution climate model outputs into finer-scale projections, making them more suitable for regional and local analyses. In the proposed approach, statistical downscaling follows a two-phase framework: in the first phase, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is employed to increase the spatial resolution of climate model data (regridding phase), and in the second phase, bias correction is performed using a quantile delta mapping technique, which statistically adjusts discrepancies between observed and simulated values (bias correction phase). The details of these two phases are provided below.

Regridding phase

An optimal resolution of 0.25° was selected as the final target to provide climate projections for the Mediterranean region. To achieve the desired resolution from the coarse GCM resolution (approximately 1°), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were employed. CNNs, widely used in artificial intelligence, are effective at extracting spatial patterns from images (LeCun et al., 2015). Within the OURMED project, different CNNs

were trained to process low-resolution images, detect spatial patterns, and generate high-resolution outputs of precipitation and temperature over the Mediterranean region.

Given that the five selected GCMs have different native grids, their data were interpolated to a common 1° resolution using xESMF, a robust Python package for conservative remapping (Zhuang et al., 2024). This ensured compatibility across the GCMs, enabling the CNN to be trained on a unified grid.

The training process used precipitation and temperature data from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset (Hersbach et al., 2020), available at the target 0.25° resolution. The use of ERA5 data is well-established in the literature and is also recommended for statistical downscaling methods in the "CORDEX experiment design and archiving specifications for statistical downscaling of CMIP6." (CORDEX, 2024). To create the training datasets, the ERA5 data for the Mediterranean region were upscaled at 1° resolution to mimic the coarse grid of GCMs and used as inputs to the CNN. The high-resolution ERA5 data (0.25°) served as the target output. This approach enabled the CNN to learn how to accurately transform low-resolution input images into high-resolution outputs while preserving spatial patterns. Each image in the CNN represents a single day of data over the Mediterranean region, processed independently without considering temporal sequences. After training, the CNN was applied to process low-resolution GCM images and generate high-resolution outputs at the 0.25° grid.

For temperature, downscaling the maximum, minimum, and mean temperatures independently could lead to unrealistic relationships between them. Therefore, three separate CNNs were trained for temperature projections: one for daily mean temperature and two for deviations in maximum and minimum temperatures from the mean. Specifically, the methodology enforces that maximum temperatures always exceed mean temperatures, which in turn are higher than minimum temperatures. Similarly, for precipitation, the CNN was trained to ensure that the regridded precipitation values never fall below zero, as negative precipitation is physically meaningless.

The CNN used for enhancing GCM spatial resolution in the MED region (**Figure 21**) consists of convolutional layers for feature extraction, a dense layer for capturing complex patterns, a dropout layer to prevent overfitting, and an output layer for high-resolution predictions. A final constraint layer ensures conservation of variables, like amount of precipitation, during regridding to maintain physical consistency. The model is trained and validated on daily data from 1970-2009 and tested on daily data from 2010-2023.

More details about the CNN characteristics are reported in Section 4.2 (Appendix).

Figure 21. CNN architecture used to enhance GCM spatial resolution in the MED region.

Table 3 presents the CNN performance, with the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) evaluated in the test phase between ERA5 0.25° data (target) and CNN outputs (predictions) at both daily and monthly scales. As an example, **Figure 22** and **Figure 23** present maps depicting daily precipitation and mean temperature for a single day, showing both the raw and regridded data for a specific model and scenario.

Table 3. RMSE evaluated in the test phase between ERA5 0.25° data and CNN outputs at daily and monthly scales over the MED region.

	Rain (mm)	Mean Temp. (°C)	Max Temp. (°C)	Min Temp. (°C)
Daily	0.83	0.23	0.31	0.43
Monthly	5.25	0.11	0.13	0.16

Figure 22. Daily precipitation (October 12, 2049) for model GFDL-ESM4 and scenario SSP126

Figure 23. Daily mean temperature (October 12, 2049) for model GFDL-ESM4 and scenario SSP126.

Bias Correction phase

Once the climate projections were regridded to the target resolution of 0.25°, a bias correction process was applied to address any systematic errors between the model projections and observed data in the control period (1985-2014). For this purpose, the Quantile Delta Mapping (QDM) method (Cannon et al., 2015) was employed, still using the ERA5 reanalysis dataset as reference. QDM ensures the relative changes projected by the model are preserved across quantiles while correcting systematic biases in the modelled outputs compared to the observed values. The QDM method involves two main steps: first, future model outputs are adjusted through quantile mapping, aligning their empirical distribution with the distribution of observed values to eliminate systematic biases. Then, the relative changes between the future and control periods, as projected by the model for each quantile, are applied to these adjusted values, resulting in bias-corrected future projections. This ensures that future projections retain the model original trend information while removing systematic errors. For minimum and maximum temperature, QDM is applied to correct deviations from the mean temperature. After correction, the maximum and minimum temperatures were reconstructed from the corrected mean and deviations, ensuring consistency with fundamental climatic principles. More details about the QDM methodology are reported in Section 4.3 (Appendix).

As an example, **Figure 24** and **Figure 25** respectively depict the empirical cumulative distribution functions (ECDFs) for precipitation and mean temperature, at a specific location (lon -4.5°, lat 33.5°) and specific model (GFDL-ESM4), comparing observed data, raw climate model outputs, and QDM-corrected projections over the historical reference period (1985–2014).

Figure 24. ECDF of observed precipitation (blue points), raw climate model output (green points), and QDM-corrected precipitation (orange points) over the historical reference period (1985–2014) at location (lon -4.5° , lat 33.5°) for model GFDL-ESM4.

Figure 25. ECDF of observed mean temperature (blue points), raw climate model output (green points), and QDM-corrected mean temperature (orange points) over the historical reference period (1985–2014) at location (lon -4.5° , lat 33.5°) for model GFDL-ESM4.

3.1.2. Demo site scale

The climate projections statistically downscaled at the MED scale served as the foundation for further downscaling at the demo site scale. For each demo site, long-term precipitation and temperature projections were downscaled both at the individual gauging stations and on a grid at 0.1° resolution, based on observational/reanalysis datasets, which covers the entire demo site.

In fact, although meteorological stations play a crucial role in site-specific analyses by providing localized data essential for detailed climate assessments, gridded datasets are utilized as a complementary resource to ensure complete spatial coverage, particularly in areas where station data is sparse or unavailable.

Also in this case, the statistical downscaling approach consisted of two steps. For each point of interest (station or grid cell centre), a Nearest Neighbour (NN) approach was first applied to extract the closest data from the projections downscaled at the Mediterranean scale. Then, the Quantile Delta Mapping (QDM) method (Section 3.1.1.1) was used to align the MED-scale downscaled projections with the observed data.

3.2. Short term climate predictions

For short-term (decadal) predictions, the OURMED project relies on data from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project 6 (CMIP6), specifically through the Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP) initiative. Its primary objective is to enhance the ability to predict climate variations over periods ranging from one to ten years, bridging the gap between seasonal forecasts and long-term climate projections. Unlike traditional climate projections, decadal predictions incorporate an initialization process, in which climate models are started from observed conditions. The DCPP framework consists of three components (Boer et al., 2016): the first focuses on producing retrospective forecasts (hindcasts) to evaluate model performance and identify systematic biases; the second generates near real-time decadal climate predictions; the third involves targeted experiments to improve the understanding of physical mechanisms that drive decadal climate variability. Similar to long-term projections, the decadal predictions rely solely on GCMs. The only scenario used within the DCPP initiative is the SSP2-4.5, representing an intermediate-emission pathway with moderate challenges in both mitigation and adaptation strategies, reflecting a middle-of-the-road approach in addressing climate change (O'Neill et al., 2017). For the OURMED project, the GCM selected for the short-term projections is the HadGEM3-GC31-MM (**Table 4**), which is used with its 10 available realizations, each offering a unique simulation of climate dynamics. These realizations stem from slightly varied initial conditions, allowing to capture a range of possible outcomes and quantify uncertainty in the projections. The decision to select a single GCM was driven by the fact that alternative models do not provide a comprehensive hindcast and forecast package with sufficiently high native resolution. The chosen HadGEM3-GC31-MM, with a resolution of 0.83° x 0.55°, is capable of delivering the required data for both retrospective and forward-looking simulations at an adequate level of detail.

Table 4. List of the selected GCMs.

	GCM institute	Model	Grid resolution (Lon x Lat)
1	MOHC	HadGEM3-GC31-MM	0.83° x 0.55°

3.2.1. Demo site scale

The short-term predictions were specifically tailored to the demo site scale, ensuring that the outcomes are highly relevant and applicable for local climate analysis, thereby supporting more informed decision-making at the local level. In particular, for each demo site, short-term precipitation and temperature predictions were downscaled both at the individual gauging stations and on a grid at 0.1° resolution, which covers the entire demo site.

The following paragraphs describe the downscaling method developed to obtain high-resolution short-term predictions.

3.2.1.1. Statistical downscaling of decadal climate predictions

For the statistical downscaling of short-term predictions, a two-phase approach was implemented, consisting of a regriding phase and a bias correction phase, similar to the methodology used for long-term projections.

Regriding phase

In the regriding phase, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was employed to enhance the spatial resolution of the climate model data. Unlike the long-term projections, where multiple GCMs were used, the short-term predictions rely on a single climate model (HadGEM3-GC31-MM). To create the training dataset, ERA5 data, available at 0.25° resolution, were upscaled to match the native grid of the climate model and used as input to the CNN. This was achieved using xESMF, a robust Python package for conservative remapping (Zhuang et al., 2024). As the target output, ERA5-Land data at 0.1° resolution were employed, providing a high-resolution reference for training. A different CNN was trained for each demo site to refine coarse climate model outputs while preserving spatial patterns at the demo site scale. As in the long-term case, independent CNNs were trained for precipitation and temperature, with one model dedicated to daily mean temperature and two others for the deviations of maximum and minimum temperatures from the mean, ensuring physically consistent relationships between them. As an example, **Figure 26** illustrates the CNN architecture designed to regrid the precipitation data for the Bode demo site.

Figure 26. CNN architecture used to enhance DCPG GCM spatial resolution at the Bode demo site.

Bias correction phase

Decadal climate prediction models often exhibit biases that depend on the lead time (the time from the start of the simulation), a phenomenon known as model drift, where simulations gradually diverge from observed climate states over time. To address these issues, hindcast experiments are employed to assess and correct lead time-dependent biases.

In decadal predictions spanning short time horizons (typically 1 to 10 years), interannual and decadal variability have a greater influence than long-term climate trends. As a result, preserving long-term trends is less critical, while model drift becomes more significant. For these reasons, the Quantile Mapping (QM) method (Panofsky & Brier, 1968) was chosen over Quantile Delta Mapping, which is used for long-term projections within OurMED. The QM method adjusts the distribution of model outputs to match observed data, improving the alignment of predictions with reality. In this case, quantile mapping is applied at each lead time to correct lead time-dependent biases, using available meteorological stations and ERA5-Land data for all demo sites as reference datasets.

3.3. Near term climate forecasts

Recent advancements in near-term climate forecasts, which extend up to several months (seasonal forecasts), have shifted from being primarily research-focused to becoming an operational activity conducted by leading meteorological institutions globally. These activities aim to estimate weather statistics over monthly and seasonal timescales, bridging the gap between traditional weather forecasts and long-term climate projections. Unlike decadal or long-term projections, near-term forecasts emphasize immediate atmospheric and climatic dynamics, providing valuable information for local resource planning and management. Conversely, unlike conventional weather forecasts, which predict specific atmospheric conditions for a given day, seasonal forecasts assess the likelihood of a season being wetter, drier, warmer, or colder than average.

For instance, the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) offers seasonal forecast products based on multi-system ensembles from leading forecasting centers, including ECMWF, The Met Office, Météo-France, Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD), Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC), National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP), Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA), and Environment and Climate Change Canada (ECCC). By integrating multiple models, C3S enhances forecast accuracy and improves the representation of uncertainties (Copernicus Climate Change Service, Climate Data Store, 2018).

Based on these or similar products, national meteorological agencies and specialized climate centers tailor near-term forecasts to national or regional scales to support localized decision-making processes.

In Italy, for example, the National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA) and various Regional Agencies for Environmental Protection (ARPA, e.g., [ARPAE seasonal forecasts](#)) provide seasonal forecasts adapted to national and regional needs. In Spain, the State Meteorological Agency (AEMET – Domínguez-Alonso et al., 2024) supplies near-term climate forecasts to support local water resource management and agricultural planning. In Germany, the German Climate Forecast System (GCFS – Fröhlich et al., 2021), developed with contributions from the German Meteorological Service (DWD), delivers high-resolution seasonal forecasts to assist stakeholders in agriculture, energy, and disaster risk management.

In the OurMED project, near-term forecasts are used at demo sites where the implemented modeling approach or early warning systems require or benefit from such simulations. In these cases, data are sourced from the relevant national or regional institutions responsible for their development. For example, the selected models for near-term forecasts at the Bode demo site are reported in **Table 5**.

Table 5. Summary of weather forecasting models selected for application in the Bode demo site, including their key characteristics.

Service Name	Models	Forecasting range	Resolution	Data format
ECMWF	1) IFS (Integrated Forecast System) 2) EPS (Ensemble Prediction System)	1) High-Resolution Forecasts: Up to 10 days. 2) Ensemble Forecasts: Up to 15 days.	Approximately 9 km for high-resolution forecasts.	GRIB2, NetCDF
DWD	1) ICON (ICOsahedral Nonhydrostatic): Global model 2) ICON-EU: Regional model 3) ICON-D2: High-resolution model for Germany and neighboring areas	1) ICON: Up to 180 hours (7.5 days) for 00 and 12 UTC runs; up to 120 hours (5 days) for 06 and 18 UTC runs. 2) ICON-EU: Up to 120 hours (5 days). 3) ICON-D2: Up to 48 hours (2 days).	1) ICON: ~13 km horizontal resolution. 2) ICON-EU: ~7 km horizontal resolution. 3) ICON-D2: ~2.2 km horizontal resolution.	GRIB2

4. Appendix

4.1. MICE imputation methods

The imputations of missing values were executed using four distinct imputation methods—random forest, predictive mean matching, linear regression, and simple random sampling—each chosen for its unique strengths and suitability for different types of data availability and relationships among variables. Below is a description of each method and its distinguishing features.

1. Random Forest (RF)

Random forest is an ensemble-based machine learning method that uses multiple decision trees to impute missing values. It predicts missing values by considering complex interactions among variables. Each tree in the ensemble is trained on random subsets of data, and predictions are aggregated (e.g., averaging for continuous data).

Strengths:

- Excellent for datasets with nonlinear relationships or complex variable interactions.
- Handles both continuous and categorical variables effectively.
- Reduces the risk of overfitting due to the ensemble nature.

Limitations:

- Computationally intensive, particularly for large datasets.

2. Predictive Mean Matching (PMM)

Predictive Mean Matching is a statistical imputation method that preserves realistic values by ensuring imputed data remain within the observed range. It works by first building a regression model using non-missing data to predict missing values. Then, for each missing entry, the method identifies observed values (donors) whose predicted values are closest to the missing value's prediction. Instead of using the predicted value directly, PMM randomly selects one of these donor values and assigns it to the missing entry, maintaining data consistency and variability.

Strengths:

- Imputed values are always plausible, as they are based on observed data.
- Ideal for continuous variables with skewed or irregular distributions.
- Avoids generating extreme or implausible values.

Limitations:

- Requires sufficient observed data to act as donors.
- May struggle with complex relationships unless additional predictors are included.

3. Linear regression

Linear regression imputes missing values by modeling the variable with missing data as a linear function of the most correlated available station (twin station). The twin station is selected based on the highest Pearson correlation with the target station requiring imputation. Missing values are replaced by the predictions generated from this regression model.

Strengths:

- Simple, computationally efficient, and interpretable.
- Effective when strong linear relationships exist between the target and the twin station.

Limitations:

- Assumes linear dependencies, which may not hold in more complex datasets.
- May produce imputed values outside the observed range.

4. Simple Random Sampling (SRS)

This method fills missing values by randomly sampling from the observed data for the same variable. It does not rely on relationships between variables or predictive models.

Strengths:

- Requires no assumptions about variable relationships.

Limitations:

- Ignores relationships between variables, potentially losing meaningful patterns.
- Best suited for exploratory analysis or situations with minimal structural requirements

4.2. Convolutional neural network

The CNNs employed to enhance the spatial resolution of long-term climate projections from GCMs for the Mediterranean region consist of several key components, which are explained below. A similar configuration was used for the CNN applied to regrid short-term climate predictions, although details of this model are not provided here for brevity.

Convolutional layer:

The network starts with two convolutional layers. Convolutional layers are designed to automatically learn spatial hierarchies from the input data, which, in this case, are the low-resolution upscaled ERA5 data. The layers use the ELU (Exponential Linear Unit) activation function, which helps the model converge faster and manage negative values better compared to traditional activation functions like ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit). The "same" padding is applied to ensure that the output feature maps retain the same spatial dimensions as the input, preserving important spatial features without downscaling prematurely.

Dense layer:

Following the convolutional layers (feature extraction), a dense layer with 3000 neurons is introduced. This fully connected layer enables the model to combine the learned spatial features into a unified representation, allowing it to understand more complex patterns and relationships in the data. By learning a dense set of weights, the network is able to capture even non-linear interactions between the features extracted in the previous layers.

Dropout layer:

To prevent overfitting, a dropout layer is applied during training. Dropout randomly sets a fraction of the neurons to zero during each training iteration, forcing the model to learn more robust and generalized features. This helps to avoid the network becoming too specialized to the training data, improving its ability to generalize to new data.

Output layer:

Finally, the output layer generates the high-resolution predictions. This layer maps the learned features from the dense layer to the desired output resolution (0.25°), providing the final downscaled outputs. This layer ensures that the final result is consistent with the target resolution, enabling the model to produce high-resolution outputs for the Mediterranean region.

Constraint layer:

An important feature of the proposed CNN architecture is the inclusion of a final and critical layer identified as the “constraint layer”. This layer ensures that the variable being regridded to a finer resolution (e.g., from 1° to 0.25°, effectively splitting one pixel into four) is preserved in the high-resolution output. For example, in the case of precipitation, the total amount of rainfall in the low-resolution pixel is conserved across the corresponding four high-resolution pixels. This design guarantees that the regridding process is conservative, maintaining the physical consistency of the variable during the resolution enhancement.

4.3. Quantile delta mapping

Quantile delta mapping (QDM) is a two-step procedure designed to correct biases in the model outputs while preserving the relative changes projected by the model.

Let $F_{obs,h}$ be the empirical cumulative distribution functions of the observed values for a given variable (e.g., temperature or precipitation) and $F_{mod,h}$ and $F_{mod,p}$ the empirical distribution functions of the modelled values in the historical and projected period, respectively. In the first step, quantile mapping adjusts the model output by aligning its distribution with the observed one. Considering the non-exceedance probability q as

$$q(t) = F_{mod,p}(x_{mod,p}(t)), \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

where $x_{mod,p}(t)$ is the model value at time t ; the modelled values are corrected according to

$$\bar{x}(t) = F_{obs,h}^{-1}(q(t)), \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

where F_{obs}^{-1} is the inverse of the empirical distribution of the observations.

Then, the relative changes in the quantiles of the model outputs are computed. Let $F_{mod,p}^{-1}$ and $F_{mod,h}^{-1}$ be the inverse of the empirical distribution of the model output for projected and historical period, respectively. The relative change in the quantile is calculated in either the additive (eq. 3) or multiplicative (eq. 4) form as follows:

$$\Delta(t) = F_{mod,p}^{-1}(q(t)) - F_{mod,h}^{-1}(q(t)) \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

$$\Delta(t) = \frac{F_{mod,p}^{-1}(q(t))}{F_{mod,h}^{-1}(q(t))} \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

This relative change is then applied to the output of eq. 2 in either the additive (eq. 5) or multiplicative (eq. 6) form:

$$\hat{x}(t) = \bar{x}(t) + \Delta(t) \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

$$\hat{x}(t) = \bar{x}(t) \cdot \Delta(t) \quad (\text{eq. 6})$$

When correcting the model outputs in the historical period $F_{mod,p} = F_{mod,h}$ and the correction follows eq. 2, as the relative changes are zero.

Setup of the QDM process for the OurMED project

During the historical control period, distributions were estimated empirically using 30-year time series (1985–2014) for observed and simulated values. The correction was performed monthly, with a 3-month window used to compute the distributions. This means that for each month (e.g., January), data from the current month and the preceding and succeeding months (i.e. December, January, and February) were combined to identify the empirical distribution. This helps account for seasonal dependencies and inter-monthly correlations. For the projection periods (2015-2100), a 30-year sliding time window centred on the year of interest was used for QDM. For example, to correct the data for January 2050, the period from 2035 to 2065 was considered, spanning 15 years before and after the target year. This dynamic approach allows to adapt to the evolving distribution of future projections, ensuring that the correction reflects both temporal shifts and long-term changes in climate patterns.

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